

CITRATE COMPLEX OF COPPER

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Copper (II) reacts with citric acid and a neutral complex, C, is formed at lower pH. The ligand occupies three-co-ordination position and the fourth co-ordination position of copper is most probably occupied by a molecule of water. The results obtained by pH titrations indicate the complex C to be a dibasic acid, dissociating successively in two steps to C_1^- and C_2^{2-} . Conductometric titration of a mixture of citric acid and copper nitrate against standard sodium hydroxide solution qualitatively supports the above results obtained by pH titration. The equilibrium constant of the reaction of the formation of C from Cu^{2+} and citric acid with the liberation of two protons and those of the reactions (i) $C \rightleftharpoons C_1^- + H^+$ and (ii) $C_1^- \rightleftharpoons C_2^{2-} + H^+$ have been determined. The probable structures of the complex have been discussed.

Many metal ions including copper form 1 : 1 complex with citrate ligand (Bobtelsky and Jordan, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1824). Much work has been done on citrate complex of copper by Meites (*ibid.*, 1950, 72, 180) and Parry and Dubois, (*ibid.*, 1952, 74, 3794). The latter workers have isolated a copper compound $Cu_2(C_6H_4O_7)$ at pH 6.5 or above.

The equilibrium constant of the reaction

has been found to be 1. The formation of the complex and its progressive changes with pH have been studied by Warner and Weber (*ibid.*, 1953, 75, 6086). Assuming citric acid to be H_3Ci , the following reactions have been proposed to be taking place with increasing pH :

Shin Suzuki (*J. Chem. Soc. Japan, Pure Chem. Sec.*, 1951, 72, 974) found the equilibrium constant of the reaction,

to be 3.37×10^{-4} by E.M.F. method. Le Febvre and Souchay (*Compt. rend.*, 1956, 248, 1416) observed that one mole of sodium hydroxide per g. atom of copper could be added to a mixture of copper and citrate solution without making the solution alkaline due to the formation of a very stable complex. Similar results were obtained by Heitner and Eliezer (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1956, 174) who titrated copper nitrate solution with trisodium citrate and mixtures of copper nitrate and different proportions of trisodium citrate against sodium hydroxide by pH titration method. The 1 : 1 complex formed by Cu(II) with citrate solution is a monobasic acid and is quantitatively neutralised by sodium hydroxide at pH 8 to 8.3. The results have also been confirmed spectro-photometrically. Le Febvre (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, 25, 553) has studied the citrate complex of copper by potentiometric surface method and the complexes $[Cu(CiH)_2]^{2-}$, $[Cu_2(Ci)_2]^{2-}$, $[Cu(Ci)_2]^{4-}$, $[Cu_2(OH)_2(Ci)_2]^{4-}$ and $[Cu(OH)_2(Ci)_2]^{6-}$ have been reported.

A good deal of investigation has been done in this laboratory on citrate complexes. The high stability of the citrate complexes has been assumed to be due to the capacity of the citrate to function as a tridentate ligand and the hydroxyl group of the ligand involved in chelation with or without liberation of a proton. The interaction of citric acid with copper therefore would afford either complex C or C_1^- , depending on whether the proton from the hydroxyl group is liberated or not. The structures may be represented as follows, assuming the co-ordination number of copper to be four and the complex is saturated with respect to co-ordination (three of the co-ordination positions are occupied by a citrate ligand and the fourth by a molecule of water).

Complex C.

(Structure I)

(Structure II)

Complex C_1^- .

(Structure III)

(Structure IV)

Whenever the complex would be formed, either two or three protons per atom of copper would be simultaneously liberated. The free carboxyl group and the co-ordinated water molecule in complex C_1^- and the free carboxyl group, the co-ordinated hydroxyl group, and possibly the co-ordinated water molecule in complex C, would successively ionise with increasing pH. This type of reactions has been observed in the investigation of nickel and cadmium citrate complexes (Pattanaik and Pani, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 619, 673). Copper is expected to behave in a similar manner. It is therefore not possible for the liberation of only one proton, as suggested in reaction (a).

The formation of a very stable complex at high pH by addition of sodium citrate to copper solution has been utilised in the estimation of trivalent antimony

and arsenic in presence of copper(II) by standard iodine (Verma and Singh, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13B, 709). Copper in the same solution is then estimated by titrating the amount of iodine liberated by addition of potassium iodide to the solution at a lower pH . The pH is lowered by addition of sulphuric and acetic acids to the solution. The results, thus obtained for copper, are a little higher than the actual amount of copper, and for this reason, standardisation of thiosulphate against similar conditions has been suggested. The standard copper solution under problem is, however, more complicated than what it appears to be. The reaction :

is reversible and pH -dependent. Above pH 4, the reaction proceeds in the forward direction almost to completion, and trivalent antimony or arsenic can be quantitatively estimated in presence of copper (II) above pH 4, if the formation of a stable citrate complex of copper is complete, so that the reaction,

would not take place. For the estimation of copper after estimating arsenic(III), the pH of the solution should be brought down so that the citrate complex would break at least partly for the reaction (ii) to take place. Due to the insolubility of cuprous iodide and in presence of excess of iodide ion, reaction (ii) can be brought about to completion. The reaction (i) in the reverse direction can be induced to proceed almost to completion in presence of a large amount of acid. At low pH therefore, the reaction (i) is expected to proceed in the reverse direction, at least to a certain extent, and the total iodine liberated would not correspond to the amount of copper(II) in the solution. It is therefore necessary to ascertain the exact pH at which the formation of the citrate complex of copper is complete, so that it would be possible to select the optimum pH at which copper can be estimated iodimetrically without any detectable influence of reaction (i). The following investigation was therefore carried out to ascertain the nature of the complex formed at different pH values.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. The pH was measured by Marconi pH meter. A solution (100 c.c.), containing 0.025 g. mol. of potassium nitrate and 0.001879 g. mol. of citric acid, was titrated against 1.016N-NaOH solution at 32°. The results are represented by the curve A in Fig. 1. Curve B represents the result obtained by titrating the same volume of solution containing the same amount of potassium nitrate and citric acid and 0.001092 g. mol. of copper nitrate against the same NaOH solution at the same temperature. Liberation of acid is indicated by the separation of the two curves. The horizontal distance between the two curves at first increases with increasing pH , reaches a maximum value and then decreases. The horizontal distance remains very nearly constant above pH 6.5. The liberation of the acid in the system containing copper is due to

the formation of a complex which is present to some extent even in pure citric acid solution.

D I S C U S S I O N

The formation of the complex from copper ion and citric acid may be represented by

where C is the complex in which the charge, if any, is not shown.

A and B are the points of intersection of curve A and B respectively by the same pH axis. The molar concentrations of the total citrate, citric acid, dihydrogen citrate, monohydrogen citrate, citrate ions and the added sodium hydroxide at A are expressed by $[\text{Ct}]$, $[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]_A$, $[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-]_A$, $[\text{HCit}^{2-}]_A$, $[\text{Cit}^{3-}]_A$ and $[\text{NaOH}]_A$ respectively. The concentrations at B are similarly expressed. The molar concentrations of total copper nitrate, copper ion and the complex at B are expressed respectively by $[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ and $[\text{C}]$. The concentrations of hydrogen ion being the same, both A and B are expressed by $[\text{H}^+]$. It can be shown, as done in the citrate complex of cadmium (Pattanaik and Pani, *loc. cit.*, p. 673) that

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - (a/b) \Delta[\text{Ct}]}{[\text{C}]} = n - (a/b) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta[\text{NaOH}] &= [\text{NaOH}]_B - [\text{NaOH}]_A \\ \Delta[\text{Ct}] &= [\text{Ct}]_B - [\text{Ct}]_A \end{aligned}$$

$$a = \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + 2 \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + 3 \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^3}$$

$$\text{and} \quad b = 1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^3}$$

k_1 , k_2 and k_3 being respectively the first, the second and the third dissociation constant of citric acid ($k_1 = 8.32 \times 10^{-4}$, $k_2 = 4.07 \times 10^{-5}$ and $k_3 = 3.24 \times 10^{-6}$; Schwarzenbac and Ackermann, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, **32**, 1682). $\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$, $\Delta[\text{Ct}]$, a and b can be calculated at different pH. When the formation of the complex is complete,

$$[\text{C}] = [\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Taking $[\text{C}]$ to be equal to $[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$, n is calculated by equation (2) at various pH values. The values thus obtained are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

pH.	$\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$ $\times 10^3$.	$-\Delta[\text{Cit}]$ $\times 10^4$.	$[\text{Cit}]_0$ $\times 10^3$.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ $\times 10^3$.	n .	$K \times 10^4$.	$K_1 \times 10^4$.	$K' \times 10^7$.	$K_2 \times 10^6$.
2.50	0.5047	0.9335	1.866	1.086	0.6802	2.83		4.78	
2.60	0.6832	1.264	1.863	1.082	0.8919	3.30		3.96	
2.70	0.7197	1.332	1.857	1.078	0.9781	2.61		2.37	
2.80	1.061	1.878	1.850	1.076	1.312	4.45		2.38	
2.90	1.140	2.109	1.846	1.073	1.494	5.05		1.71	
3.00	1.245	2.301	1.841	1.070	1.663	6.48		1.23	
3.10	1.288	2.384	1.836	1.068	1.764	7.39		0.787	
3.20	1.344	2.485	1.833	1.065	1.882			0.570	
3.30	1.407	2.603	1.830	1.064	2.049			0.461	
3.40	1.480	2.737	1.826	1.061	2.177		0.855	0.312	
3.50	1.543	2.854	1.823	1.059	2.314		1.44	0.250	
3.60	1.605	2.970	1.819	1.057	2.467		2.20	0.220	
3.70	1.696	3.137	1.813	1.054	2.632		3.42	0.237	
3.80	1.769	3.272	1.811	1.053	2.802		6.71	0.331	
4.00	1.814	3.355	1.805	1.049	2.970				
4.25	1.945	3.598	1.798	1.048	3.313				2.56
4.50	1.884	3.484	1.791	1.041	3.478				2.90
4.75	1.852	3.404	1.787	1.039	3.687				3.90
5.00	1.747	3.230	1.783	1.036	3.794				3.85
5.50	1.545	2.858	1.776	1.032	3.871				2.14
6.00	1.257	2.324	1.770	1.029	4.037				
7.00	1.041	1.924	1.764	1.025	4.040				
8.00	0.5636	1.793	1.761	1.023	4.000				

n increases with increasing pH and is < 1 within pH 2.5 to 2.6. Above pH 2.7 and up to pH 3.2, the value is > 1 and < 2 . The value of n is > 2 above pH 3.3 and > 3 above pH 4. The value above pH 5.75 is 4 and remains constant up to pH 8 or above.

It is very probable that a neutral complex, C, is first formed due to the interaction of a copper ion and a molecule of citric acid with the liberation of two protons (reaction 1). The equilibrium constant may be given by

$$\frac{[\text{C}] \times [\text{H}^+]^2}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]} = K \quad \dots \quad (1-1)$$

[C] is calculated by equation (2) taking the value of n to be 2. The values are recorded in Table I. The mean value of K is 4.59×10^{-6} , which is in agreement with that obtained by Shin Suzuki (*loc.cit.*). It can be shown that

$$[\text{Cit}]_0 - [\text{C}] = b [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_0 \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}]_0$ is calculated by equation (4) and $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ is obtained by subtracting [C] from $[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$. The values of K calculated are shown in Table I. The complex C above pH 3.3 dissociates like an acid.

The dissociation constant K_1 is given by

$$\frac{[C_1^-] \times [H^+]}{[C]} = K_1 \quad \dots \quad (5-1)$$

It is assumed that the dissociation of C takes place after its complete formation. The whole of the copper above pH 3.3 is present as C and C_1^- . Hence,

$$[Cu(NO_3)_2] = [C] + [C_1^-] \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Acid liberated due to the formation of the complex is $2[C] + 3[C_1^-]$. Hence

$$\frac{2[C] + 3[C_1^-]}{[Cu(NO_3)_2]} = n$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{[C_1^-]}{[Cu(NO_3)_2]} = n - 2 \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \frac{[C]}{[Cu(NO_3)_2]} = 3 - n \quad \dots \quad (7-1)$$

K_1 can be calculated by equation (5-1) substituting respectively $[C_1^-]/[Cu(NO_3)_2]$ and $[C]/[Cu(NO_3)_2]$, i.e., $(n-2)$ and $(3-n)$ in place of $[C_1^-]$ and $[C]$. The values of K_1 , thus obtained, are shown in Table I. It is interesting to note that neither K nor K_1 is strictly constant. This might be due to existence of C beyond pH 3.3 and the formation of C_1^- begins below pH 3.3. The values of K and K_1 improve if calculations are made from the results of another experiment (Table II) at 33° in which the concentration of citric acid is nearly ten times that of copper nitrate. Curve A in Fig. 2 represents the pH titration of 110 c.c. of the solution containing 0.01063 g. mol. of citric acid against 1.02N-NaOH and curve B represents that of another 110 c.c. solution containing the same amount of citric acid and 0.001092 g. mol. of copper nitrate, against the same NaOH solution. In this experiment the value of n is never < 1 as proposed by Warner and Weber at lower pH (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5086).

TABLE II

pH.	$\Delta[NaOH] \times 10^3$.	$-\Delta[Ca] \times 10^3$.	$[Ca]_s \times 10^3$.	$[Cu(NO_3)_2] \times 10^3$.	n .	$K \times 10^4$.	$K_1 \times 10^4$.	$K' \times 10^4$.
2.30	0.9772	1.033	9.521	9.786	1.159	3.94		88.30
2.40	1.065	1.110	9.461	9.723	1.293	3.42		55.10
2.50	1.299	1.353	9.410	9.672	1.677	4.72		43.00
2.60	1.364	1.421	9.353	9.612	1.714	5.04		27.20
2.70	1.429	1.489	9.303	9.561	1.850	6.92		17.40
2.80	1.492	1.544	9.245	9.501	2.002			11.60
2.90	1.478	1.539	9.200	9.456	2.056		2.66	6.82
3.00	1.538	1.601	9.143	9.397	2.210		3.09	4.80
3.10	1.516	1.579	9.080	9.330	2.280		3.81	3.00
3.20	1.498	1.561	9.026	9.276	2.324		4.13	1.93
3.30	1.480	1.541	8.973	9.222	2.432		4.01	1.31
3.40	1.461	1.522	8.910	9.162	2.509		5.36	0.91
3.50	1.443	1.503	8.861	9.107	2.559		5.26	0.614
3.60	1.427	1.489	8.810	9.055	2.681		6.58	0.520
3.70	1.409	1.468	8.751	9.001	2.725			0.400
3.80	1.462	1.522	8.720	8.943	2.806			0.355
3.90	1.443	1.503	8.644	8.884	3.009			

If it is assumed that Cu^{2+} reacts with citric acid affording C_1^- and three protons are simultaneously liberated, the equilibrium constant of the reaction would be given by

$$\frac{[\text{C}_1^-] \times [\text{H}^+]^3}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times [\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]} = K' \quad \dots \quad (1-2)$$

The calculations are made according to the above assumption and the values of K' are shown in Tables I and II. In either case K' is not constant but decreases with increasing $p\text{H}$, and becomes very nearly constant at the higher $p\text{H}$ range, where n lies between 2 and 3 and the concentration of C_1^- is appreciable. The value of the K' is also not of the same order in the two experiments. Three protons are therefore not liberated at a time. The complex C is first formed and it dissociates into C_1^- and H^+ at a higher $p\text{H}$, as suggested before.

At still higher $p\text{H}$, n is > 3 and the complex C_1^- dissociates like an acid. The reaction and the equilibrium constant K_2 are expressed by equation (8) and (8-1) respectively.

$$\frac{[\text{C}_2^{2-}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}_1^-]} = K_2 \quad \dots \quad (8-1)$$

Assuming the formation of C_1^- to be complete when n is > 3 , K_2 can be calculated by equation (8-2) as before.

$$\frac{(n-3) \times [\text{H}^+]}{(4-n)} = K_2 \quad \dots \quad (8-2)$$

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The values of K_2 calculated are shown in Table I and can be taken as constants, the average value being 2.87×10^{-5} .

Structure of the Complex:

Complex C most probably has structure (I) or structure (II), cited before. Since malic acid also furnishes a similar neutral complex (Nanda and Pauli, unpublished), the structure (I) appears to be more probable. The structure (II), however, cannot be completely ruled out. Assuming structure (I) to be the structure of complex C, the structure of C_1^- may be represented by

The structure of C_2^{2-} may be represented either by structure (V) or (VI), shown below, depending on whether the proton is liberated from the co-ordinated hydroxyl group or water molecule.

The formation of complex C, C_1^- and C_2^{2-} is also indicated by the conductometric titration of a mixture of 10 c.c. of 0.1092M copper nitrate and 20 c.c. of 0.09396M citric acid, diluted nearly to 150 c.c. against 1.016N-NaOH. The conductance (Fig. 3) first decreases due to the formation of the neutral complex C and the neutralisation of the acid and then remains very nearly constant probably due to the formation of both C and C_1^- and then rises when the formation of C is complete. When the formation of C_1^- is complete, it rises more rapidly due to the conversion of C_1^- to C_2^{2-} . The final break in the curve comes when the formation of C_2^{2-} is complete, and the very rapid increase in the conductance is due to the addition of sodium hydroxide only.

Copper ion exists in solution below pH 3.0, when the ratio of copper to citric acid is nearly 1:2, and below pH 2.7, when copper to citrate ratio is 1:10; copper ion is expected to react with iodide ion only, when free copper ions are available in the solution. The reduction of copper (II) to copper (I) by iodide ion would depend on the ratio of copper to citrate and also on pH. The higher the proportion of citrate, the lower would be the pH at which the reaction would take place. If the concentration of

citrate is ten times the concentration of copper, the pH should be < 2.7 , and at this pH arsenate is expected to be reduced, at least partly, by iodide ion.

FIG. 3

The results of iodometric titration of 25 c.c. of (0.1M-CuSO₄) solution against sodium thiosulphate (25 c.c. of CuSO₄ solution $\equiv$ 24.9 c.c. of sodium thiosulphate solution) in presence of 25 c.c. of 0.2M sodium citrate at different pH values are recorded

in Table III. The pH has been altered by addition of known amounts of approximately $0.5N \cdot H_2SO_4$ acid or $0.1N \cdot NaOH$.

The above results indicate that when copper to citrate ratio is 1:2, the estimation of copper can be done at pH 3.11 or below. Above pH 3.11 copper (II) is incompletely reduced to copper (I). There is no reduction of copper at pH 7. The complex formed at pH 7 is therefore very stable. It is of interest to note that CuI precipitated at pH 3.11 or below in presence of citrate ligand can be completely oxidised and brought into solution by increasing the pH with $NaOH$. The above results further indicate that a mixture of copper salt and sodium citrate requires one equivalent of acid per atom of copper for neutralisation and can be estimated by pH titration even in presence of excess of sodium citrate.

TABLE III

pH .	$Na_2S_2O_3$ reqd.	Colour of the soln. at the end-point.
2.50	24.90 c.c.	
2.79	24.90	
3.11	24.90	
3.52	19.80-23	Greenish blue
4.12	13.20-15.00	Do
4.98	7.00	"
5.34	4.75	Bluish
5.57	1.95	Do
5.95	0.80	"
7.05	0.00	Deep blue

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